

Research article

Coupling (reduced) Graphene Oxide to Mammalian Primary Cortical Neurons *In Vitro*

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Abstract: Neuronal nanoscale interfacing aims at identifying or designing nanostructured smart materials and validating their applications as novel biocompatible scaffolds with active properties for neuronal networks formation, nerve regeneration, and bidirectional biosignal coupling. Among several carbon-based nanomaterials, Graphene recently attracted great interest for biological applications, given its unique mechanical, optical, electronic properties, and its recent technological applications. Here we explore the use of Graphene Oxide (GO) and reduced Graphene Oxide (rGO) as biocompatible culture substrates for primary neuronal networks developing *ex vivo*. We quantitatively studied cytotoxicity and cellular viability as well as single-cell and network-level electrophysiological properties of neurons *in vitro*. Our results confirm previous reports, employing

48 immortalized cell lines or pluripotent stem cells, and extend them to mammalian primary cortical
49 neurons: GO and rGO are biocompatible substrates and do not alter neuronal excitable properties.

50
51 **Keywords:** Graphene oxide; Neuroengineering; Primary neuronal cultures; cellular
52 electrophysiology; cytotoxicity

53 54 **1. Introduction**

55 Our fundamental understanding of brain (dys)functions is today at a cross-road. While decades
56 of concerted research led to immense progresses in the field, understanding, repairing, or enhancing
57 the brain still represent the greatest challenges in science and engineering. Recently, advances in
58 nanotechnologies paved the way to a potential revolution in Neuroscience, inspiring many
59 investigators and offering novel tools for studying the brain at the nanoscale [1]. Progresses in
60 material science in particular offered novel perspectives for identifying new ways of repairing and
61 interfacing the brain at the cellular and molecular levels. In fact, micro- and nanostructured materials
62 display intriguing geometrical similarities with the (sub)cellular organization of brain, and have been
63 repeatedly considered as a potential new substrate for engineering future neuroprosthetics [2,3] and
64 novel electrodiodes. Ultimately, the goal is developing micro- and nanosized sensors and actuators,
65 capable of functional interfacing with the biological tissue and with individual nerve cells at
66 mechanical, chemical, and electrical levels. At the same time, interest for overcoming existing
67 limitations of microfabrication technologies and conventional *in vitro* interfacing techniques [4,5],
68 inherently leading to 2-dimensional neuronal networks, increasingly became widespread. Thus,
69 active research started on 3-dimensional scaffolding for the formation of functional neuronal
70 networks [6] and of brain-like layered tissue [7,8].

71 Along these lines, Graphene [9,10] as well as other Carbon-based nanomaterials such as Carbon
72 nanotubes became extremely interesting for Neuroscientists, who started numerous studies on their
73 exploitation a nanoscale electrodes, hybrid devices, or nanostructured substrates for neuronal growth
74 and regeneration [2,3,11], investing on their unrivalled electrochemical properties [12-19]. Graphene
75 in particular, a 2D monoatomic layer of C atoms arranged in a honeycomb lattice, is the youngest
76 member of Carbon-based nanomaterials family. Its existence has been first reported in 2004 [13],
77 and rapidly attracted huge attention, as proved by the more than 10'000 papers published on this
78 topic.

79 Existing biological investigations of Graphene Oxide (GO) and reduced Graphene Oxide (rGO)
80 are becoming increasingly common and today they range from drug delivery and gene therapy [20]
81 to biosensors [21], as well as from electrodes for electrical extracellular stimulation of excitable cells
82 [22] to photothermal tumour ablation therapy [23] and tissue scaffolding [24]. In Neuroscience, GO
83 and rGO have been so far considered as substrates for the growth of neurons [25,26] and for the
84 differentiation of stem cells [27,28], as well as employed as 3-dimensional scaffolds for neural stem
85 cells [29]. Furthermore, Graphene has also recently been exploited in the fabrication of transparent
86 neural electrode arrays [30,31] for both *in vivo* and *ex vivo* electrophysiological and neuroimaging
87 applications. As these applications could lead to long-term, or even chronic, Graphene electrodes
88 implants, we feel that investigations of the elementary properties of GO and rGO in terms of
89 cytotoxicity as well as alteration of the electrical phenotype of cells and networks as observed with
90 other nanostructured materials [2,11], deserves more attention. Particularly the use of primary
91 mammalian neurons instead of pluripotent or immortalised cell lines is of great importance for future
92 preclinical translation studies.

93 In this brief contribution, we compare the properties of GO and rGO, obtained by spin coating
94 onto conventional glass coverslips, as substrates for neuronal growth, studying their biocompatibility
95 and whether the electrical properties of neurons and networks are altered.

96 97 **2. Materials and Methods**

98 99 *2.1 GO and rGO substrates preparation and characterization*

100 GO substrates were prepared by spin coating (2000 rpm, 30 s) GO solution (2mg/ml; Graphene
101 Supermarket, USA) over glass coverslips.

102 Reduction of GO into rGO was carried electrochemically (Autolab Potentiostat, Metrohm,
103 Singapore), upon immersing GO/glass substrates into a Sodium Phosphate buffer solution (pH =
104 4.5). The substrates were connected to a working electrode, while an Ag/AgCl electrode and a Pt
105 mesh were used as reference and counter electrodes, respectively. Chronoamperometry was used
106 holding GO/glass substrates at -0.9V for 1 min. Substrates were then rinsed with deionized water and
107 dried on a heater at 100°C for 2 min. The morphology of GO and rGO flakes was characterised by
108 Scanning Electron Microscopy (Fig. 1a-b) (SEM; FEGSEM JSM 7600F, Jeol, USA), while Atomic
109 Force Microscopy (AFM, ICON-PKG, Bruker, USA) was employed to determine the thickness of
110 GO and rGO layers (Fig. 1d-e) by characterising the boundary of the GO/rGO layer and the glass,
111 after exposing by localised minimal scratching the underlying glass layer (Fig. 1d). Raman spectra of
112 GO and rGO substrates were finally acquired with a spectrometer (excitation wavelength: 488 nm;
113 Jobin Yvon T64000, Horiba, Japan) at backscattering configuration (Fig. 1c).

114 115 *2.2 Culturing of mammalian primary cortical neurons*

116 GO/rGO were employed as substrate for neuronal culturing and compared to control conditions,
117 represented by the use of standard glass coverslips. To ensure microbiological sterility, all GO/rGO
118 and control substrates were first autoclaved, upon high-pressure saturated steam at 121 °C for 30 min
119 (SA-260FA, Sturdy Industrial Co., LTD, Taiwan). All substrates were then coated with
120 Polyethyleneimine (PEI, Sigma-Aldrich, Belgium) [32], by soaking their surface in a 0.1% PEI
121 solution (w/v) overnight, and afterwards rinsed in deionized water and left drying at room
122 temperature, prior to cell seeding. No adequate cell adhesion was ever observed in the lack of PEI
123 treatment (not shown).

124 Rat primary neuronal cultures were obtained by standard methods and in accordance with
125 national and institutional guidelines on animal experimentation. Briefly, cortices were dissected from
126 newborn (i.e., postnatal day 0) Wistar rats (Charles River, France), sliced, digested in a trypsin
127 solution (0.025%), and then mechanically dissociated, using repeated passage through the tip of a
128 small glass pipette. Prior to seeding, cells were centrifuged and suspended in Modified Essential
129 Medium supplemented with 50µg/mL gentamycin, 2M glucose, 5% horse serum, and 200mM l-
130 glutamine (Sigma-Aldrich, Belgium). Cells were seeded at a density of $\sim 1000 \text{ mm}^{-2}$, ensuring rapid
131 maturation of fully functional neuronal networks *ex vivo* [33].

132 133 *2.3 Cell viability*

134 To assess GO/rGO substrates biocompatibility in terms of cell adhesion and viability, the
135 Live/Dead Cell double staining assay kit (Sigma-Aldrich, Belgium) was performed in neuronal

136 cultures 9 days *in vitro* (DIVs) after plating. Four coverslips for each of the three conditions (i.e.,
137 control, GO and rGO), obtained over two distinct culture preparations, were stained. Digital photos
138 from six distinct fields of view for each sample (Fig. 2a-c) were acquired using a fluorescence
139 microscope (BX51, Olympus Life Sciences, Belgium) with green (U-MWIBA3, 460-495 nm) and
140 red (U-MWIGA3, 530-550nm) filters, equipped with a digital camera (DP71, Olympus Life
141 Sciences, Belgium). The CellSens software (Olympus Life Sciences, Belgium) was used for image
142 acquisition. Cells were counted using the Cell Counter plugin of ImageJ 1.47v analysis system [34],
143 and densities of alive cells were computed as the average across 24 different images (Fig. 2d-e).

144 To indirectly quantify cell plasma membrane damage or rupture, and thus evaluate cytotoxicity
145 of GO and rGO, the lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) assay test (Sigma Aldrich, Belgium) was used at 9
146 DIVs. Cell viability was calculated (Fig. 2f) as reported in literature [35,36].
147

148 2.4 Cellular electrophysiology

149 Whole-cell patch-clamp electrophysiological recordings were carried out at 34°C from the soma
150 of neurons, at 9-13 DIVs. Intracellular electrical signals were amplified by an Axon Multiclamp
151 700B Amplifier (Molecular Devices, USA), under voltage- or current-clamp, controlled by the LCG
152 software [37]. Patch pipettes were pulled from standard borosilicate glass (1B150F-4, World
153 Precision Instruments, USA) and filled with solution containing (in mM): 135 K-gluconate, 4 NaCl,
154 10 HEPES, 10 PC-Na₂, 0.2 EGTA, 4 ATP-Mg²⁺, and 0.3 GTP-Na₂; pH 7.3 titrated with KOH,
155 resulting in an electrical impedance of 6-8 MΩ. The extracellular solution contained (in mM): 145
156 NaCl, 4 KCl, 2 Na-pyruvate, 5 Hepes, 5 glucose, 2 CaCl₂, and 1 MgCl₂; pH adjusted to 7.4 with
157 NaOH. In order to assess passive and excitable electrical properties of single neurons, *ad hoc* current
158 stimulation step-waveforms were injected to estimate the effective membrane time constant and the
159 apparent input resistance (Fig. 3a-d). Estimates of the resting membrane potential, as well as the
160 spontaneous emission of action potential were obtained without injecting any stimulus (Fig. 4). All
161 recordings were analysed using custom MATLAB scripts (The Mathworks, Natick, USA).
162

163 2.5 Statistical analysis

164 The normality of each data set was tested by the Lilliefors test and subsequent statistical
165 analysis was performed accordingly. For non-normal distributions, Wilcoxon rank sum test was
166 used, while Student's t-test was employed otherwise. Statistical significance has been reported in the
167 figures as $p < 0.05$ (*), $p < 0.005$ (**), and $p < 0.0005$ (***). Data are presented as percentage ±
168 ratio error, as mean ± standard error of the mean (SEM) for normal distributions, and as median and
169 interquartile range otherwise.
170

171 3. Results and Discussion

172 173 3.1 Characterization of the rGO/GO substrates

174 Substrates were characterized using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM, Fig. 1a-b), Atomic
175 Force Microscopy (AFM, Fig. 1d-e), and Raman spectroscopy (Fig. 1c). SEM revealed an excellent
176 coverage of GO and rGO flakes, over the entire surface of the glass substrates (Fig. 1a-b).

177 The Raman spectra of GO and rGO samples reveal two of dominant peaks, D and G, present in
178 Graphene [38-40], centered at 1361 and 1603 cm⁻¹ for GO, and at 1351 and 1575 cm⁻¹ for rGO (Fig.

179 1c). As expected, the ratio of the amplitude of those peaks increases, confirming the successful GO
180 reduction [41,42].

181 The height profile of deposited Graphene was obtained by AFM at the boundary between
182 rGO/GO and the underlying glass, and revealed a 4 nm thick layer for both samples, with a root
183 mean square value of 2.4 nm (Fig. 1d-e).
184

185
186 **Figure 1:** Characterization of the rGO/GO substrates. Images of GO (a) and rGO (b) spin-coated on
187 glass, obtained by scanning electron microscopy with a 5000 times magnification, reveal an even
188 distribution of the flakes on the entire glass substrate. Spectra of rGO/GO (c) show peaks at
189 characteristic Raman shifts typical of Graphene, while Atomic Force Microscopy shows a 4 nm high
190 step profile (e) at the boundary between rGO/GO and the underlying glass substrate, exposed upon
191 scratching (d).

192
193 **3.2 Cell viability**

194 A standard assay for cell viability, based on bath application of calcein AM and ethidium
195 homodimer-1 solutions and their read out by epifluorescence, was employed to perform a
196 quantitative analysis of cell viability upon measurements of (live) cell density (Fig. 2a-c). The
197 quantification of microscopy images revealed as expected that the total cell density after 9 DIVs
198 decreased to ~50% of the initial seeding density, for both control and rGO. However, the cell density
199 decreased to ~35% of the initial seeding density, for GO substrates (Fig. 2d). Interestingly however,
200 the percentage of living cells of out the total calculated for each condition was not significantly
201 different across the conditions, including GO and rGO. Although GO substrates are atomically
202 rougher than rGO [43,44] and thus in principle more likely to promote neuronal adhesion, its
203 superficial charge is known to be more negative than rGO [45,46]. We speculate that the last
204 property might have been then predominant, under our culture conditions, and determining a lower
205 cell adhesion performance in GO compared to rGO and control conditions [47].

206 We also assessed cytotoxicity of GO and rGO by the lactate dehydrogenase assay (LDH, Sigma
 207 Aldrich, Belgium) and observed generally higher membrane damage for neurons grown on GO and
 208 rGO, with respect to control conditions (Fig. 2f). While this is partly at odd with the clear results of
 209 overall cell viability and cellular electrophysiology (Fig. 3-4), incongruity might be attributed to
 210 suboptimal properties of the Graphene surface coating, prior to cell seeding (i.e., by PEI), or to
 211 incompatibility of the LDH assay with the Graphene substrate.
 212

213
 214 **Figure 2:** Viability and cytotoxicity of culture substrates. Fluorescence microscopy images (a-c)
 215 show living (green) and dead (red) cells. Cell densities (d) and their fraction (e) are quantified by
 216 automated cell count and referred to individual substrates. Further cytotoxicity tests revealed
 217 potential suboptimal Graphene surface treatment, when compared to control conditions.

218
 219 *3.3 Cellular Electrophysiology*

220 To investigate the electrical phenotype of neuronal cells growing and establishing functional
 221 neuronal networks on GO and rGO substrates, patch-clamp recordings were performed. Live
 222 neurons, identified under differential interference contrast videomicroscopy by their morphology and
 223 their ability to respond with a sustained train of action potential upon external electrical stimulation,

224 were recorded in whole-cell configuration, after establishing a giga-ohm seal from the cell somata. A
 225 variety of current-clamp stimulation waveforms were injected somatically, in order to infer the
 226 passive and excitable electrical properties of neuronal membranes (Fig. 3). These were the
 227 membrane time constant (τ , Fig. 3a), the apparent input resistance (R, Fig. 3b), the resting membrane
 228 potential (E, Fig. 3c), the cell capacitance (C, Fig. 3d), the width of action potentials (APs) at half-
 229 amplitude (Δ , Fig. 3e-d), the peak AP amplitude (Fig. 3g), the AP threshold (Fig. 3h), and the rate of
 230 AP emission evoked by external DC current pulses (Fig. 3i). Passive properties (R, E, C, τ) did not
 231 significantly differed for neurons grown on GO and rGO, compared to control conditions, and also
 232 active membrane properties were comparable, with the exception of the peak AP amplitude that was
 233 slightly, but significantly larger on GO and rGO, compared to control. Importantly, the functional
 234 relationships between the output AP rate and the input injected current amplitude (Fig. 3i) of neurons
 235 growing on GO and rGO were undistinguishable, upon removing to each neuron its own rheobase
 236 current, for the sake of comparison. Small but significant differences were instead observed solely on
 237 the peak AP amplitude (Fig. 3e), potentially attributed to marginal heterogeneity of ionic channels
 238 expression, (e.g., K_V) whose density and membrane distribution is known to affect AP shape [48].
 239

240

241 **Figure 3:** Single-cell passive and excitable electrical phenotype is largely unaffected by the growth
 242 substrate. No differences were observed for membrane time constant τ , input resistance R, resting
 243 potential E, and membrane capacitance C (a-d). Similarly, active excitable electrical properties (e-h;
 244 f, Control: n = 23, GO: n = 19, rGO: n = 18; i, Control: n = 16, GO: n = 14, rGO: n = 16) were
 245 unaltered, with the minor yet significant exception of the AP peak amplitude (e). Values inside
 246 histograms indicate the number of patched neurons (a-e, g-h).

247 The same recording technique, enable us to indirectly infer network properties, by monitoring
 248 the spontaneous AP firing rate and frequency of AP burst discharges (Fig. 4). When compared to
 249 control conditions, neuronal networks formed on GO and rGO had slightly higher spontaneous

250 activity (Fig. 4a-b), significant for GO only, suggesting an earlier formation of synaptic connections
251 or marginally stronger synaptic connectivity than control. Representative intracellular recordings of
252 spontaneous activity are shown in Fig. 4c-d.

253 A corresponding increase in spontaneous postsynaptic currents amplitudes, measured with GO
254 under voltage-clamp conditions, was also observed (not shown).

255 While distinct network-level electrical phenotype have been reported for neurons coupled to
256 conductive thin-films of carbon nanotubes [11,49], and attributed to specific electrical properties of
257 the substrate [2], GO and rGO seem to largely leave neuronal network formation *ex vivo* unaltered.
258

259
260

261 **Figure 4:** Network-level electrical phenotype is largely unaffected by the growth substrate. No
262 major differences were observed for the rate of spontaneous occurrence of Aps (a) and of bursts of
263 APs (b), as also demonstrated by representative raw intracellular voltage recordings (c-d). Values
264 above box-and-whisker plots (a) and inside histograms (b) indicate the number of patched neurons.

265

266

267 Nonetheless, neurons and neural stem cells growing on Graphene [25] and surface-modified GO
268 [47] have increased length and number of neurites [50], which might account for enhanced network
269 connectivity and thus explain the observed increased network activity, despite the reduction in
270 absolute number of neurons. Indeed, number of neurons, efficacy of excitatory synaptic connections
271 or their overall number all influences the rate of spontaneous electrical activity *in vitro* [51]. We
272 hypothesize therefore that the slightly increased spontaneous AP firing, observed for neurons grown
273 on GO, is the result of an increased number or efficacy of excitatory synaptic connections rather than
274 a consequence of the absolute number of viable cells. This is supported by the well-known
275 homeostatic scaling of synaptic efficacy [55] and by the variation in the ration of synapses-per-
276 neuron during neuronal maturation [56].

277 On the other side, it has been demonstrated that firing frequency depends on neuronal density
278 [52-54]: very dense cultures or very sparse display lower levels of spontaneous AP firing, than
279 medium dense cultures. Here, we observed generally both a decreased total number of adhered cells
280 and an increased spontaneous activity on GO, confirming the relationship between density and
281 activity, while excluding a direct alteration of network formation by GO.

282 Similarly, no significant differences were observed also in the rate of occurrence of bursts of
283 APs (Fig. 4b), further indicating that recurrent excitatory connections were not altered by GO or rGO
284 [51].

285

286

287 **4. Conclusions**

288 In this brief report we presented, to the best of our knowledge, a first quantitative comparison
289 between GO and rGO as substrates for neuronal growth, employing mammalian primary cortical
290 neurons. We found that GO and rGO are suitable candidates for neuronal interfacing, though rGO
291 displayed better performances than GO, and that both allow the formation of a fully developed and
292 active neuronal network. The electrical phenotype of individual neurons did not appeared altered by
293 the choice of the substrate, while small but significant differences were found in the spontaneous rate
294 of AP firing, greater for neurons grown on GO with respect to both control and rGO conditions.

295

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303 publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

304

305 **Contributions**

306 AMM and AM performed electrophysiological experiments, analysed data and wrote the paper.
307 JM performed the viability studies and earlier electrophysiological experiments. FV characterized
308 GO and rGO substrates. AMHN prepared and characterized GO and rGO substrates. LKP, MN, and
309 MG designed and supervised the research. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

310 **Conflict of Interest**

311 All authors declare no conflict of interest in this paper.

312

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